

ANALYSIS OF BENDING AND TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF CFRP STRANDED AND SPIRAL CABLES USING A NUMERIC MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) cables present outstanding performance in terms of specific stiffness and strength. However, the behavior of such cables is not yet fully understood. Out of the possible architectures, Spiral cables are known for having better tensile strength than Stranded cables, while Stranded cables, better bending properties. In this study, a CFRP Spiral composite cable was analyzed in order to evaluate their bending and tensile behavior as compared to a similar Stranded composite cable. The following systems were studied: (i) a standard 6×7 Stranded cable composed of 49 rods (wires) and (ii) 1×61 Spiral (61 rods), all using 3 mm diameter rods. These cables have the same nominal diameter of 27 mm. In all, the Ordinary Lay (OL) and Lang Lay (LL) constructions for tensile stress are similar. The 1×61 Spiral cable showed the highest rupture load among the studied cables (1,034 kN) in contrast to 927 kN from the 6×7 Stranded cable. The minimum bending radius (MBR) was calculated, and the 1×61 Spiral cable presented the highest MBR (618 mm). The gain in the rupture load for the Spiral cable (11.5%) is higher than the gain of MBR compared with the 6×7 Stranded cable (4.2%).

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) cables are lighter cables with better performance in terms of specific stiffness and strength and also higher fatigue and corrosion resistance when compared to traditional steel cables, being natural candidates for harsh environments such as offshore applications. There are only a few experimental data available in the literature for these new cables and theoretical solutions still need to be further developed. On the other hand, several theoretical approaches have been developed for isotropic cables (metallic wire ropes), some of them with many simplifications nonetheless still showing good agreement compared to experimental data.

According to Meier [1], composite cables are much more recent for industrial applications, and in order to encourage their use in structural applications, it is necessary to fully study and understand their behavior, which could be translated as evaluating analytical solutions, constructing numerical models and executing experimental tests. Costello [2] extensively investigated isotropic cables developing analytical models based on beam theory, and unlike most of the previous analytical solutions, he treated the wires as rods, allowing bending and torsion stiffness analysis. Costello [2] also proposed an easy way to evaluate fatigue life of a rope running around a sheave and submitted to normal stresses.

Ordinary Lay (OL) is a stranded rope in which the direction of lay of the wires in the outer strands is in the opposite direction to the lay of the outer strands in the rope, and Lang Lay (LL) is a stranded rope in which the direction of lay of the wires in the outer strands is in the same direction as the lay of the outer strands in the rope [3].

Usabiaga & Pagalday [4], also using beam theory, developed an analytical solution for OL and LL cables (Fig. 1) submitted to tensile stress allowing for rod rotation, neglecting, however, the Poisson effect. They compared their model with Costello [2] analytical solution for Poisson ratio of 0.0 and 0.3 and verified a small difference. However, the cable behavior was greatly influenced by rod rotation

when the cable was submitted to torque. They also showed that the resulting torque at the cable ends is higher in the LL construction, i.e. when both wires and strands have the same lay direction. Different from the OL, where the wires are twist in the opposite direction from the strands.

Figure 1: Representation of cable construction [4].

On the numerical field, Erdonmez & Imrak [5] analyzed a 6×7 Stranded cables through FEM (Finite Element Method). They started investigating the minimum length to be modeled that could still give a trustable result for any cable length, saving computational time and guaranteeing that the contact between wires effectively occur. They executed both frictionless elastic (multi-layered) and frictional elastic-plastic (single layered) analyses and compared them with Costello [2] analytical solution. They found good agreement between the predictions and concluded that the wire contraction played a small role on the mechanical behavior. They also stated that their model could be applied to a bending condition instead of only tensile stress. In fact, Jiang [6] analyzed isotropic cables in pure bending considering plastic strain and friction and also achieved good agreement with Costello [2] analytical solution. He analyzed only single-layered strands, but suggested that his work could be extended to multi-layered strand cables.

Ghoreishi *et al.* [7] compared their FEM model results with experimental data for a 1×7 single-layered cable under axial loading, varying the helix angle, and obtained small variations. They also analyzed the same cable through nine different analytical models, including Costello [2] with different considerations and assumptions. Ghoreishi *et al.* [7] constructed a stiffness matrix with four elements: axial stiffness and torsion in the main diagonal and coupling terms in the secondary diagonal. They plotted the four elements of the cable stiffness matrix in order to compare each of them with his numerical data, varying the helix angle from 60° to 90°. All models that did not underestimate torsional stiffness provided good results for helix angles above 75°, or 70° for the models that considered the Poisson's effect. As the helix angle decreased, only the FEM remained accurate, with a trustable solution.

CFRP cables are traditionally manufactured by pultrusion using epoxy resin, allowing for the use of long fibers and high fiber volume fraction. Their importance is verified nowadays mainly on the civil engineering sector. Meier [1] investigated the advantages of using CFRP cables for structural applications in suspended structures. Due to CFRP cables properties, like corrosion resistance and high specific strength, he decided to evaluate the maximum bridge span allowed by both, steel cables and CFRP cables. He found that, for classical suspension bridges, steel cables could support a span up to 7.7 km, while CFRP cables up to 37.5 km. Meier [1] also pointed out two drawbacks in using CFRP cables. The first is related to their weak wind erosion and ultraviolet attack resistance, which could be easily solved by using polyethylene layer as shielding. The second is their higher initial design cost compared to steel cables. Motoyama *et al.* [8] highlighted the lightweight, high strength, no-magnetism and corrosion resistance of a commercial CFRP cable, extending its usage for the aerospace industry as stowage of satellite for transportation, and as a viable way to reduce weight in deployable structures.

Regarding the petroleum industry, composite materials are not new in this sector, as cited by Eckold [9]. Glass reinforced materials have already been used in pipelines, salt water disposal, casing, surface injection, flow and gathering lines, mainly because they offer both design and operational advantages, such as lightweight and corrosion resistance. Jackson *et al.* [10] analyzed the use of Carbon Fiber Composite Cable (CFCC), a commercial CFRP cable developed by Tokyo Rope for mobile offshore drilling units, and compared existing cable technologies, shown in Fig. 2. In this figure, CFCC, Nippon Steel Carbon Fiber Cable (NACC) and Leadline (commercial product developed by Mitsubishi Plastics)

are carbon fiber derivatives. They also showed the superiority in mechanical properties of carbon fibers relatively to many synthetic materials, stating that CFCC are an excellent solution for the Oil & Gas industry.

Figure 2: Comparison of specific modulus and strength of different cable materials [10].

Odrú & Geffroy [11] studied the use of CFCC in the offshore industry, more specifically in TLP (Tension Leg Platforms) used to extract oil in ultra-deep waters. The advantages reported by them include: good fatigue resistance, high level of flexibility, safety due to the non-propagation of defects, as found in bulk materials, and unlimited size for mooring. They also mention that the tested characteristics of one sample was able to represent the behavior of the entire cable.

In this study, a CFRP Spiral composite cable was analyzed in order to evaluate their bending and tensile behavior as compared to a similar Stranded composite cable.

2 NUMERICAL MODEL

2.1 Geometry and mesh

All the CFRP cables studied in this work were based on commercial products and they are shown in terms of architecture, rod material and nominal diameter in Table 1. The material properties applied in the computational model were also based on the commercial products materials and they are shown in Table 2, a transversely isotropic behavior was assumed. The 6×7 Stranded cable and 1×61 Spiral both have the same nominal diameter of 27 mm.

A 3D draw of each cable was created using a commercial CAD software and the numerical model was developed within the commercial finite element platform AbaqusTM. All the cables were studied with the OL and LL constructions for future comparison. For the 6×7 Stranded cable a single-pitch of 1000 mm and a double-pitch of 3000 mm were used for being more suitable in case of a prototype being produced for a possible future work. For the Spiral cable, in order to keep the same rate diameter/length of the 6×7 Stranded Cable, the pitches presented in Fig. 3 were used. A length of 100 mm were applied for all cables; this short length was used in order to reduce computational time. However, this length (3.34% of the pitch) is still the length where both contact and sliding exist [12]. In Fig. 3 the negative pitches indicates that those layers were twisted on the opposite direction from the positive ones (OL).

Table 1: Cables specifications in terms of architecture, number of rods and geometry.

Cable name	6×7 Stranded cable	1×61 Spiral cable
Architecture	Stranded	Spiral
Number of rods	49	61
Rod material	Carbon fiber + Epoxy resin	Carbon fiber + Epoxy resin
Rod diameter	3 mm	3 mm
Nominal Ø	27 mm	27 mm

Table 2: CFRP 3D elastic properties used in the model.

$E_1 = 147.6 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{12} = 2.87 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{12} = 0.28$
$E_2 = 8.61 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{13} = 2.87 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{13} = 0.28$
$E_3 = 8.61 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{23} = 3.60 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{23} = 0.02$

Figure 3: 3D draw of the 1×61 Spiral cable with Ordinary Lay construction with the given pitches.

A tetrahedral mesh using a ten-node linear brick element with three degrees of freedom per node designed as C3D10 in Abaqus™ element library was applied for both Stranded (Fig. 4a) and Spiral (Fig. 4b) cables for being a suitable adaptation for the complex geometry of the cables. For the 6×7 Stranded cable the model used about 264,400 nodes and 900,000 elements, for the Spiral 1×61 Cable, 21,300 nodes and 71,800 elements.

Figure 4: Tetrahedral mesh used on the numerical model for the a) Stranded and b) 1x61 Spiral cables.

2.2 Contact and Boundary Conditions

The surface-to-surface contact type was defined between surfaces of the individual adjacent wires of the strand. Surface-to-surface contact interactions describe contacts between wires in the individual layers and between wire layers caused by the tensile load acting on the strand. This approach gives results that are more accurate but time-consuming [13]. The principle of surface-to-surface contact type method for the contacts between the wires in the individual layers and contacts between the wire layers of the strand is shown for the 6x7 Stranded Cable in Figs. 5a and 5b, respectively. Friction was modeled with a friction coefficient of 0.6, experimentally measured in [14].

Figure 5: Contact pairs between a) rods and b) strands for the 6x7 Stranded cable.

Two different cases were studied in this work: (i) pure tensile stress and (ii) pure bending. For the case (i), one of the cable's end was built-in, not allowing displacement or torsion in any direction. On the other end, torsion along the longitudinal (z) axis was disabled and a tensile force was applied on all transversal section surface according to Fig. 6. For the case (ii), in one of the ends the displacement in x , y and z and the rotation over y and z were disabled, enabling only free rotation over the x -axis. On the other end, only the rotation in x and displacement in z were allowed. A bending moment were applied in both ends, however with opposite orientations.

Figure 6: Tensile stress application schematic on 6×7 Stranded cable.

2.3 Numerical Model Verification

In order to verify the developed numerical model, the work of Erdonmez & Imrak [5] was used as comparison. For that, the presented FEM model was fed with the same geometry, material properties and boundary conditions as in [5]: an isotropic material cable (1020 steel) and a Stranded 6×7 architecture as can be seen in the Fig. 7 (similar to the 6×7 Stranded cable studied at this present work). This work also use a computational model, however, the authors validated their results with experimental results. An axial force of 350 kN has been applied and the Fig. 8 shows comparatively the tensile stress results for both models. The same linear behavior can be observed, showing a good relation between the two models. However, the Erdonmez & Imrak [5] curve is slightly less rigid compared to the presented model, which can be explain by the different element used for both models, hexahedral and tetrahedral, respectively. Nevertheless, this difference is relatively low, 3.2%.

Figure 7: Isotropic material cable studied by Erdonmez & Imrak [5].

Figure 8: Force vs Strain comparison between Erdonmez & Imrak [5] and the presented model.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Pure Tensile Stress

All the studied cables were simulated for a pure tensile stress. The failure criteria used was the rod maximum strain, which for this material is 1.9% [15]. Figure 9 shows the curves for Force vs. Strain for the 6×7 Stranded Cable with free-end and fixed-end conditions and for the OL and LL constructions.

Figure 9: Force vs. Strain for the 6×7 Stranded cable with free-end and fixed-end conditions and for the Ordinary and Lang Lay constructions.

The results for the OL and LL did not showed a significant difference for this kind of mechanical solicitation, the curves are overlapped showing the same mechanical behavior, different from the torque analysis where the construction play an important role. The dotted curves stands for the free-end condition, this is a comparative analysis only since on a field application a cable will work with a fixed-end condition. However, a lower stiffness can be observed in these cables compared to the fixed-end construction, which can be explain by the higher degree of freedom present in this system, where the rotation along the axial axis provides a bigger displacement for the cables.

Figure 10 shows the curves Force vs. Strain for the 1×61 Spiral cable with the constructions OL, LL and Parallel, where all the rods are distributed over an infinite pitch. These Spiral cable have a similar behavior compared with the 6×7 Stranded cable for a tensile load. The LL constructions are slightly less rigid than the OL and for the 1×61 Spiral cable the curves are overlapped. It can observed that the rupture loads are lower compared to the Parallel versions of the same respective cable. This behavior is harder to observe on the 6×7 Stranded cable (~5%). For the 1×61 Spiral cable (OL and LL) the rupture load is about 13% lower when compared to its Parallel version.

Figure 10: Force vs. Strain for the 1x61 Spiral cable with the OL, LL and Parallel constructions.

After analyzed the tensile strength, the rupture load of all cables were compared. Fig. 11 shows the different rupture loads for an axial load for all the different cables with OL construction and fixed-end condition. As previously discussed, the rod quantity and the nominal diameter of the cables are not the same. The 1x61 Spiral cable have a higher rod quantity (61) and so the higher rupture load (1,034 kN). The 6x7 Stranded cable have 49 rods, about 20% less than the 1x61 Spiral, and a rupture load of 927 kN, 10% lower compared with the same Spiral cable. In conclusion, even with 20% more rods, the rupture load for the Spiral cable is 10% higher than the 6x7 Stranded cable.

Figure 11: Rupture load for the studied cables.

3.2 Pure Bending

All the cables studied for the pure bending simulation used OL construction. Figure 12 shows for illustrative purposes the behavior for the 6x7 Stranded cable when a load of 1×10^5 N.mm was applied, which was the given bending applies for all cases. Figure 12a show it with a 3D lateral view and Fig. 12b an isometric view. It can be observed in Fig. 12a that in the upper region of the cable a tensile load occur, and in the lower region, compression, which goes with load applied.

Figure 12: 6×7 Stranded cable with a) lateral and b) isometric view when a bending load is applied.

The results of (i) rotational displacement over the longitudinal axis and (ii) longitudinal strain of the outermost rod generated with the numerical model were imported into a spreadsheet. With this information was possible to calculate the cables bending radius, bending angle and flexural rigidity. Figure 13 shows the bending radius vs outermost rod strain, however this curve is for a maximum bending moment of 1×10^5 N.mm. With an extrapolation from the exponential fit curve the maximum bending radius was calculated for the maximum rod strain of 1.9%. This extrapolation was necessary due the high complexity of the model, where the solution diverge close to the rupture strain. Therefore, a lower load is applied and the extrapolation is made.

Figure 13: Maximum outermost rod strain vs. bending radius for the 6×7 Stranded cable.

Figure 14 shows the minimum bending radius (MBR), which is minimum radius a cable can be bend without rod rupture. The MBR in the Spiral cable increases with the increases of the cable nominal radius with a linear relationship, since the quotient between MBR and cable nominal diameter is 22. The 6×7 Stranded cable presented the lower MBR compared with the 1×61 Spiral cable, which can be explain by the lower quantity of rods and a different architecture, more suitable for bending.

Table 3 compares the rupture load with the MBR, it can be observed that the rupture load increases

in 11.5% from the Stranded to the 1×61 Spiral cable. However, there is gain of only 4.2% in terms of MBR for the same cables.

Figure 14: Minimum bending radius for all the studied cables calculated from the numerical model.

Table 3: Rupture load and minimum bending radius for all the studied cables.

	1×61 Spiral	
Rupture Load (kN)	927	1034
Minimum Bending Radius (mm)	593	618

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work different composite cables, architectures and conditions were analyzed in terms of tensile and bending stresses. The OL and LL constructions for a tensile stress are similar. The 1×61 Spiral cable showed the highest rupture load among the studied cables, 1,034 kN against 927 kN from the 6×7 Stranded cable. The minimum bending radius was calculated, and the 1×61 Spiral cable presented the highest MBR (618 mm). The Spiral cables have a linear relation between the nominal diameter and the MBR, which does not occur with the 6×7 Stranded cables. The gain in the rupture load for the Spiral cable (11.5%) is higher than the gain of MBR compared with the 6×7 Stranded cable (4.2%).

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